

Performance and stability of PtCo alloy catalysts in high-temperature polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells – Supplementary Information

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Contents

S1	Data analysis	3
S2	ECSA development measurements	4
S3	Membrane masses before and after doping	5
S4	Electrode delamination.....	5
S5	GDL diffractogram.....	6
S6	Dynamic load curves and U-I curves	7
S7	XANES of the delaminated electrodes and membranes	10
S8	EXAFS analysis	12
S9	Calculations of nanoparticle dimensions from $ECSA_{CO}$ and surface from XRD 25	
S10	XRD of commercial $Co_3(PO_4)_2$	26
S11	Effect of PtCo on both electrodes	27

S1 Data analysis

Various programs were used in the scope of this work. Electrochemical impedance spectra were fitted in Measurement Model (University of Florida Research Foundation, Inc.) to the equivalent circuit shown in **Figure S1**, consisting of a resistor (Ohmic resistance of the whole cell, primarily the membrane), and two or three parallelly connected sets of a resistor (electrode kinetics) and a constant phase element (electrode|membrane interface). The CO stripping and hydrogen underpotential deposition (H_{UPD}) voltammetry data were analysed in the Nova 2.1 program (Metrohm) to obtain electrochemically active surface areas $ECSA_{CO}$ and $ECSA_{HUPD}$, respectively. The single-cell H_{UPD} U - I curves were corrected for capacitive currents and integrated between times corresponding to voltages of 240 and 100 mV to obtain relevant and comparable results. Analogously, the CO stripping curves were corrected using a baseline; however, the voltage integration interval varied among the measurements due to changes in the catalyst layer, such as nanoparticle growth and surface roughness increase. Tafel analysis was carried out using MATLAB 2023b software (MathWorks) and its built-in function “polyfit”.

Figure S1: Equivalent circuit used in the scope of this work, from left to right: a resistor, and a series of two or three parallelly connected couples (in parentheses) of a resistor and a constant phase element (CPE) of the anode ($R_{CT,A}$), the cathode ($R_{CT,C}$), and the low-frequency (mass transport) resistance (R_{MT}).

S2 ECSA development measurements

For the H_{UPD} measurement, the flow of O_2 on the cathode was stopped and N_2 was introduced instead, the anode was flushed with H_2 ($20\text{ cm}^3\text{ min}^{-1}$) the cathode with N_2 ($50\text{ cm}^3\text{ min}^{-1}$) for 10 min. Then, both gases were redirected to a humidification chamber, made of Nafion tubing (Permapure) submerged in deionised water, attaining 100 % relative humidity at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, before reaching the cell. Thus, humidified gases were fed to the cell for additional 10 min. After that, the N_2 valve was closed and a constant cell voltage of 0.4 V was set for 30 s while keeping the flow of H_2 on the anode. Then, the voltage was cycled ($0.4\text{ V} \rightarrow 1\text{ V} \rightarrow 0\text{ V} \rightarrow 1\text{ V} \rightarrow 0\text{ V} \rightarrow 1\text{ V}$) at a sweep rate of 20 mV s^{-1} . The whole sequence was repeated twice and the cathode was flushed with humidified N_2 before the second measurement for 10 min.

Afterwards, the cathode compartment was again flushed with N_2 ($50\text{ cm}^3\text{ min}^{-1}$) for 10 min and then for 10 min with humidified (demi water, $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) mixture of N_2 ($40\text{ cm}^3\text{ min}^{-1}$) and CO ($2\text{ cm}^3\text{ min}^{-1}$). The anode was still flushed with $20\text{ cm}^3\text{ min}^{-1}$ of H_2 for those 20 min, during the second half also with humidification. After this, the cathode compartment was flushed with humidified N_2 ($50\text{ cm}^3\text{ min}^{-1}$) for 50 s to remove excess, i.e. non-adsorbed, CO . The N_2 valve was then closed and the measurement started with the same settings as H_{UPD} : $0.4\text{ V} \rightarrow 1\text{ V} \rightarrow 0\text{ V} \rightarrow 1\text{ V}$ with a scan rate of 20 mV s^{-1} . Again, the whole measurement sequence was repeated twice.

S3 *Membrane masses before and after doping*

Figure S2: Mass of Advent TPS membranes before and after doping procedure for each tested membrane-electrode assembly (MEA).

S4 *Electrode delamination*

Figure S3: Scheme of MEA delamination with arrows symbolising how XRD was measured.

S5 *GDL diffractogram*

Figure S4: X-ray diffractogram of the gas-diffusion layer (GDL).

S6 Dynamic load curves and U-I curves

Figure S5: IR-compensated dynamic load curves of the experimental single cell after 24, 72 and 144 h with various catalysts on the electrodes: A, B, C—HiSPEC4000 (Pt/C) on the anode and either Pt-Co alloy catalyst on Ketjenblack support (PtCo/KB), Pt-Co alloy catalyst on reduced graphene oxide support (PtCo/rGO), or Pt/C on the cathode; D, E, F—Pt/C on the cathode and PtCo/KB, PtCo/rGO, or Pt/C on the anode; G, H, I—Pt/C, PtCo/KB, or PtCo/rGO on both electrodes. Cell temperature 180 °C, hydrogen feed on the anode, oxygen feed on the cathode, voltage sweep rate of 5 mV s⁻¹. Description of experiment duration and the type of catalyst on the electrode is included in figure inset.

Figure S6: Tafel plots evaluated from the IR-compensated dynamic load curves of experimental single cell after 24, 72, and 144 h with various catalysts on the electrodes: A, B, C—HiSPEC4000 (Pt/C) on the anode and either Pt-Co alloy catalyst on Ketjenblack support (PtCo/KB), Pt-Co alloy catalyst on reduced graphene oxide support (PtCo/rGO), or Pt/C on the cathode; D, E, F—Pt/C on the cathode and PtCo/KB, PtCo/rGO, or Pt/C on the anode; G, H, I—Pt/C, PtCo/KB, or PtCo/rGO on both electrodes. Cell temperature 180 °C, hydrogen and oxygen feed, voltage sweep rate of 5 mV s⁻¹. The description of experiment duration and the type of catalyst on the electrode is included in the figure inset.

Figure S7: U-I (A, B, C, G, H, K, L) and CO stripping U-I curves (D, E, F, I, J, M, N) of cathode under nitrogen flow in experimental single cells after 24, 72, and 144 h with various catalysts on the electrodes, anode was always used as a pseudo-reference electrode under gaseous hydrogen flow: A, B, C, D, E, F—HiSPEC4000(Pt/C) on the anode and a Pt-Co alloy catalyst either on Ketjenblack support (PtCo/KB) or on reduced graphene oxide support (PtCo/rGO) on the cathode; G, H, I, J—PtCo/KB or PtCo/rGO on the anode and Pt/C on the cathode; K, L, M, N—PtCo/KB or PtCo/rGO on both electrodes. Cell temperature 180 °C, hydrogen flow on the anode 20 cm³ min⁻¹, nitrogen flow on the cathode 50 cm³ min⁻¹, voltage sweep rate of 20 mV s⁻¹. The description of experiment duration and type of catalyst on the electrode is included in the figure inset.

S7 *XANES of the delaminated electrodes and membranes*

Figure S8: XANES of MEA C and pristine Pt/C, measured at the Pt L₃-edge.

Figure S9: XANES of MEAs with the PtCo catalysts, measured at the Pt L₃-edge.

Figure S10: XANES of MEA C and pristine Pt/C, measured at the Co K-edge.

S8 EXAFS analysis

Figure S11: EXAFS analysis results in bar plots for all post mortem samples, based on Pt L₃-edge. A – N_{Pt-Pt} of MEA C; B – N_{Pt-O} of MEA C; C–H – KB MEAs on the left (green), rGO MEAs on the right (blue), C, D – N_{Pt-Pt} ; E, F – N_{Pt-Co} ; G, H – N_{Pt-O} . Fits with errors between 50 and 100 % are marked with an asterisk, errors over 100 % are marked with a double cross.

Figure S12: EXAFS analysis results in bar plots for all post mortem samples, based on Co K-edge, KB MEAs on the left (green), rGO MEAs on the right (blue). A, B – N_{Co-Co} ; C, D – N_{Co-Pt} ; E, F – N_{Co-O} . Fits with errors between 50 and 100 % are marked with an asterisk; errors over 100 % are marked with a double cross.

Table S1: EXAFS fit parameters for Pt/C at the Pt L₃-edge.

Pt/C pristine			
#	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.756	2.012	10.85
error	0.0053	0.02	-
σ / Å	0.0775	0.0908	-
error	0.0086	0.027	-
N	4.11	1.72	-
error	1.1	0.65	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.012	0.017	-
error	0.003	0.01	-
MEA C anode			
#	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.759	1.995	10.85
error	0.0051	0.031	-
σ / Å	0.0711	0.0641	-
error	0.0044	0.039	-
N	7.23	0.696	-
error	0.94	0.5	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0101	0.00823	-
error	0.0013	0.013	-
MEA C membrane			
#	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.762	1.98	10.85
error	0.0045	0.032	-
σ / Å	0.0683	0.0316*	-
error	0.0041	-	-

N	7.71	0.387	-
error	0.89	0.2	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0093	0.002*	-
error	0.0011	-	-
MEA C cathode			
#	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.763	1.961*	10.85
error	0.0017	-	-
σ / Å	0.0651	0.0316*	-
error	0.0035	-	-
N	8.73	0*	-
error	0.84	-	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0085	0.002*	-
error	0.0009	-	-

Table S2: EXAFS fit parameters for PtCo/KB at the Pt L₃-edge.

PtCo/KB pristine				
#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.659	2.721	2.002	10.08
error	0.023	0.0093	0.023	-
σ / Å	0.0842	0.0793	0.092	-
error	0.038	0.013	0.031	-
N	1.17	4.12	1.54	-
error	0.96	1.8	0.65	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.014	0.013	0.017	-
error	0.011	0.004	0.011	-

MEA KBc anode				
#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.65*	2.754	1.971	10.08
error	-	0.0043	0.02	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0779	0.0316*	-
error	-	0.0036	-	-
N	0*	8.61	0.594	-
error	-	1	0.19	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.012	0.002*	-
error	-	0.001	-	-

MEA KBc membrane				
#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.65*	2.753	1.968	10.08
error	-	0.0044	0.02	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.078	0.0316*	-
error	-	0.0036	-	-
N	0*	8.48	0.591	-
error	-	1	0.19	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.012	0.002*	-
error	-	0.001	-	-

MEA KBc cathode				
#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.65*	2.741	1.956	10.08
error	-	0.004	0.029	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0816	0.0316*	-
error	-	0.0032	-	-
N	0*	10.4	0.4	-
error	-	1.1	0.19	-

$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.013	0.002*	-
error	-	0.001	-	-

MEA KBa anode				
#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.669	2.714	1.984	13.02
error	0.027	0.0061	0.027	-
σ / Å	0.0698	0.0903	0.0743	-
error	0.036	0.0048	0.046	-
N	0.806	8.58	0.971	-
error	0.84	1.4	0.54	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.00973	0.016	0.011	-
error	0.013	0.002	0.011	-

MEA KBa membrane				
#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.674	2.726	1.988	13.02
error	0.045	0.0057	0.02	-
σ / Å	0.0638	0.0899	0.0316*	-
error	0.057	0.0045	-	-
N	0.435	8.89	0.598	-
error	0.81	1.3	0.2	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.00813	0.016	0.002*	-
error	0.021	0.002	-	-

MEA KBa cathode				
#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.65*	2.757	1.955	13.02
error	-	0.0031	0.027	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0727	0.0316*	-

error	-	0.0027	-	-
N	0*	10.6	0.444	-
error	-	0.92	0.19	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.011	0.002*	-
error	-	0.001	-	-

MEA KBb anode

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.676	2.717	1.983	14.49
error	0.03	0.0061	0.033	-
σ / Å	0.0628	0.0893	0.0905	-
error	0.041	0.0048	0.043	-
N	0.657	8.31	1.14	-
error	0.78	1.3	0.64	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0079	0.016	0.016	-
error	0.014	0.002	0.014	-

MEA KBb membrane

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.674	2.728	1.986	11.31
error	0.047	0.0057	0.017	-
σ / Å	0.0605	0.0891	0.0316*	-
error	0.061	0.0045	-	-
N	0.392	8.51	0.736	-
error	0.78	1.3	0.2	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.00732	0.016	0.002*	-
error	0.022	0.002	-	-

MEA KBb cathode

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.65*	2.743	1.961	9.221
error	-	0.0039	0.028	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0801	0.0316*	-
error	-	0.0031	-	-
N	0*	10.4	0.416	-
error	-	1.1	0.19	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.013	0.002*	-
error	-	0.001	-	-

Table S3: EXAFS fit parameters for PtCo/rGO at the Pt L₃-edge.

PtCo/rGo pristine

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.651	2.715	2.01	9.876
error	0.019	0.011	0.03	-
σ / Å	0.0818	0.0767	0.0994	-
error	0.028	0.014	0.031	-
N	1.48	3.53	1.68	-
error	0.93	1.7	0.7	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.013	0.012	0.02	-
error	0.009	0.004	0.012	-

MEA rGOc anode

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.65*	2.752	1.964	9.876
error	-	0.0042	0.022	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0774	0.0316*	-

error	-	0.0035	-	-
N	0*	8.69	0.544	-
error	-	1	0.19	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.012	0.002*	-
error	-	0.0011	-	-

MEA rGOc membrane

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.65*	2.746	1.969	9.876
error	-	0.0025	0.022	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0796	0.0316*	-
error	-	0.0037	-	-
N	0*	8.65	0.542	-
error	-	1.1	0.19	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.0127	0.002*	-
error	-	0.0012	-	-

MEA rGOc cathode

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.65*	2.741	1.967	9.876
error	-	0.0024	0.025	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0825	0.0316*	-
error	-	0.0033	-	-
N	0*	9.97	0.468	-
error	-	1.1	0.19	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.014	0.002*	-
error	-	0.001	-	-

MEA rGOa anode

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.665	2.71	1.996	15.78
error	0.027	0.0056	0.024	-
σ / Å	0.0785	0.0914	0.0316*	-
error	0.048	0.0044	-	-
N	0.98	9.59	0.515	-
error	0.95	1.4	0.2	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0123	0.017	0.002*	-
error	0.012	0.002	-	-

MEA rGOa membrane

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.678	2.736	1.977	10.71
error	0.057	0.0048	0.022	-
σ / Å	0.0704	0.0862	0.0316*	-
error	0.065	0.0037	-	-
N	0.385	9.57	0.54	-
error	0.87	1.2	0.19	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0099	0.015	0.002*	-
error	0.027	0.001	-	-

MEA rGOa cathode

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.65*	2.757	1.955	11.48
error	-	0.0031	0.024	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0735	0.0316*	-
error	-	0.0026	-	-
N	0*	11	0.487	-
error	-	0.93	0.19	-

$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.011	0.002*	-
error	-	0.001	-	-

MEA rGO_b anode

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.667	2.706	1.979	16.59
error	0.026	0.0057	0.024	-
σ / Å	0.0811	0.0914	0.0316*	-
error	0.038	0.0044	-	-
N	1.12	9.45	0.514	-
error	0.98	1.4	0.2	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0131	0.017	0.002*	-
error	0.011	0.002	-	-

MEA rGO_b membrane

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.68	2.723	1.974	11.67
error	0.037	0.0051	0.027	-
σ / Å	0.0688	0.088	0.0316*	-
error	0.044	0.004	-	-
N	0.625	9.57	0.447	-
error	0.85	1.3	0.19	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.00946	0.016	0.002*	-
error	0.016	0.001	-	-

MEA rGO_b cathode

#	Pt-Co	Pt-Pt	Pt-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.65*	2.747	1.984	11.88
error	-	0.0042	0.018	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0823	0.0316*	-

error	-	0.0033	-	-
N	0*	9.93	0.655	-
error	-	1.1	0.19	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.014	0.002*	-
error	-	0.001	-	-

Table S4: EXAFS fit parameters for PtCo/KB at the Co K-edge.

PtCo/KB pristine

#	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.612	2.683	2.013	8.721
error	0.025	0.011	0.044	-
σ / Å	0.105	0.0828	0.0316*	-
error	0.024	0.011	-	-
N	2.34	5.12	0.369	-
error	1.1	1.8	0.24	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.022	0.0137	0.002*	-
error	0.0097	0.0037	-	-

MEA KB_c cathode

#	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.575	2.714	2.07	16.7
error	0.021	0.013	0.017	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0316*	0.0316*	-
error	-	-	-	-
N	0.737	1.8	1.97	-
error	0.11	0.2	0.23	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.002*	0.002*	-
error	-	-	-	-

MEA KBa anode				
#	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.618	2.688	2.016	11.43
error	0.015	0.014	0.023	-
σ / Å	0.0693	0.0828	0.0316*	-
error	0.021	0.013	-	-
N	1.68	4.83	0.721	-
error	0.67	1.9	0.24	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0096	0.0137	0.002*	-
error	0.0055	0.0043	-	-

MEA KBa membrane				
#	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.626	2.679	2.028	11.43
error	0.019	0.0084	0.028	-
σ / Å	0.0956	0.0705	0.0316*	-
error	0.018	0.012	-	-
N	2.71	4.7	0.614	-
error	0.96	1.6	0.24	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0183	0.00995	0.002*	-
error	0.0068	0.0034	-	-

MEA KBb anode				
#	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.65	2.781	2.125	17.95
error	0.01	0.011	0.0087	-
σ / Å	0.0177	0.0316*	0.0809	-
error	0.042	-	0.014	-
N	0.801	0.868	3.59	-
error	0.44	0.33	0.66	-

$2\sigma^2$	0.00063	0.002*	0.0131	-
error	0.0066	-	0.0046	-

MEA KBb membrane				
#	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.615	2.707	2.038	17.95
error	0.015	0.018	0.018	-
σ / Å	0.0567	0.0808	0.0316*	-
error	0.025	0.019	-	-
N	1.2	4.27	1.15	-
error	0.6	2.2	0.27	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.00642	0.0131	0.002*	-
error	0.0068	0.0058	-	-

MEA KBb cathode				
#	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.518	2.655	1.982	17.95
error	0.05	0.027	0.032	-
σ / Å	0.109	0.0585	0.0316*	-
error	0.037	0.027	-	-
N	2.96	2.4	1.32	-
error	1.9	2	0.46	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0237	0.00685	0.002*	-
error	0.015	0.0078	-	-

Table S5: EXAFS fit parameters for PtCo/rGO at the Co K-edge

PtCo/rGO pristine				
	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
#				
R / Å	2.618	2.672	2.003	11.76
error	0.049	0.014	0.032	-
σ / Å	0.12	0.0826	0.0316	-
error	0.058	0.015	0.06	-
N	2.18	4.25	0.872	-
error	2.9	1.8	0.91	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0287	0.0136	0.002	-
error	0.035	0.0048	0.015	-

MEA rGOc membrane				
	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
#				
R / Å	2.595	2.708	2.042	11.76
error	0.012	0.0097	0.012	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0316*	0.0316*	-
error	-	-	-	-
N	1.11	1.79	1.89	-
error	0.13	0.2	0.22	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.002*	0.002*	-
error	-	-	-	-

MEA rGOc cathode				
	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
#				
R / Å	2.604	2.73	2.055	11.76
error	0.026	0.041	0.024	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.1*	0.0771	-
error	-	-	0.021	-

N	0.751	2.02	3.6	-
error	0.2	1.4	1	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.02*	0.0119	-
error	-	-	0.0062	-

MEA rGOa anode				
	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
#				
R / Å	2.607	2.674	2.021	15.42
error	0.019	0.016	0.018	-
σ / Å	0.083	0.0812	0.0316*	-
error	0.024	0.017	-	-
N	1.77	3.9	1.14	-
error	0.82	2	0.26	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0138	0.0132	0.002*	-
error	0.0076	0.0054	-	-

MEA rGOa membrane				
	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
#				
R / Å	2.618	2.731	2.054	15.42
error	0.011	0.0089	0.014	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0316*	0.0316*	-
error	-	-	-	-
N	1.31	2.11	1.39	-
error	0.13	0.21	0.21	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.002*	0.002*	-
error	-	-	-	-

MEA rGOa cathode				
	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
#				
R / Å	-	-	2.057	15.42

error	-	-	0.0083	-
σ / Å	-	-	0.0662	-
error	-	-	0.0076	-
N	-	-	5.95	-
error	-	-	0.6	-
$2\sigma^2$	-	-	0.0088	-
error	-	-	0.002	-

MEA rGOB anode

#	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.567	2.679	2.025	11.47
error	0.03	0.031	0.028	-
σ / Å	0.0868	0.0638	0.0316*	-
error	0.042	0.029	-	-
N	1.56	2.55	1.46	-
error	1.1	2.4	0.44	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.0151	0.00815	0.002*	-
error	0.018	0.0092	-	-

MEA rGOB membrane

#	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.613	2.664	2.019	11.47
error	0.014	0.025	0.015	-
σ / Å	0.0686	0.105	0.0316*	-
error	0.021	0.02	-	-
N	1.69	5.16	1.21	-
error	0.72	3.3	0.27	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.00943	0.0222	0.002*	-
error	0.0055	0.0084	-	-

MEA rGOB cathode

#	Co-Co	Co-Pt	Co-O	R-factor filtered
R / Å	2.614	2.71*	2.06	11.47
error	0.027	-	0.012	-
σ / Å	0.0316*	0.0316*	0.0803	-
error	-	-	0.0094	-
N	0.272	0*	5.72	-
error	0.11	-	0.75	-
$2\sigma^2$	0.002*	0.002*	0.0129	-
error	-	-	0.003	-

Figure S13: EXAFS plots in R and k spaces at the Pt L₃-edge for the catalyst Pt/C. In the figure, “exp” and “mod” mean “experimental data” and “fit model”, respectively.

Figure S14: EXAFS plots in R and k spaces at the Pt L₃-edge for the catalyst PtCo/KB. In the figure, “exp” and “mod” mean “experimental data” and “fit model”, respectively.

Figure S15: EXAFS plots in R and k spaces at the $Pt L_3$ -edge for the catalyst $PtCo/rGO$. In the figure, “exp” and “mod” mean “experimental data” and “fit model”, respectively.

Figure S16: EXAFS plots in the R and K space at the $Co K$ -edge for the catalyst $PtCo/KB$. In the figure, “exp” and “mod” mean “experimental data” and “fit model”, respectively.

Figure S17: EXAFS plots in R and k spaces at the Co K-edge for the catalyst PtCo/rGO. In the figure, “exp” and “mod” mean “experimental data” and “fit model”, respectively.

S9 Calculations of nanoparticle dimensions from $ECSA_{CO}$ and surface from XRD

Table S6: Surface area of Pt on cathode calculated from XRD-derived mean nanoparticle dimensions and its comparison to ECSA measured by CO-stripping; colours in the ratio columns indicate the cathode catalyst (Pt/C – red, PtCo/KB – green, PtCo/rGO – blue).

MEA code	XRD			CO stripping		
	$ECSA_{0h} / m^2 g^{-1}$	$ECSA_{144h} / m^2 g^{-1}$	$ECSA_{144h} / ECSA_{0h}$	$ECSA_{24h} / m^2 g^{-1}$	$ECSA_{144h} / m^2 g^{-1}$	$ECSA_{144h} / ECSA_{24h}$
C	52.78	27.16	0.51	30.89	21.13	0.68
KBc	65.09	48.02	0.74	30.03	23.55	0.78
rGOc	55.99	41.99	0.75	38.92	30.97	0.80
KBa	52.78	28.55	0.54	29.62	22.71	0.77
rGOa	52.78	29.45	0.56	28.72	19.90	0.69
KBb	65.09	49.65	0.76	42.96	27.22	0.63
rGOb	55.99	55.99	1.00	45.12	33.72	0.75

Table S7: Nanoparticle dimensions calculated from $ECSA_{CO}$ surfaces and their comparison to XRD-derived mean nanoparticle dimensions; colours in the ratio columns indicate the cathode catalyst (Pt/C – red, PtCo/KB – green, PtCo/rGO – blue).

MEA code	CO stripping			XRD		
	d_{24h} / nm	d_{144h} / nm	d_{144h} / d_{0h}	d_{24h} / nm	d_{144h} / nm	d_{144h} / d_{0h}
C	9.06	13.24	1.46	5.3	10.3	1.94
KBc	9.75	12.44	1.27	4.5	6.1	1.36
rGOc	7.77	9.76	1.26	5.4	7.2	1.33
KBa	9.44	12.32	1.30	5.3	9.8	1.85
rGOa	9.74	14.06	1.44	5.3	9.5	1.79
KBb	6.49	8.69	1.44	4.5	5.9	1.31
rGOb	6.70	8.97	1.34	5.4	5.4	1.00

S10 XRD of commercial $\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$

Figure S18: X-ray diffractogram of commercial $\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$.

S11 Effect of PtCo on both electrodes

Figure S19 shows the results of the experiments with PtCo catalysts on both electrodes.

Figure S19: Results of testing protocol for MEAs with Pt/C on the cathode and various catalysts on both electrodes, see plot inset. A, B, C – stationary load and power density curves after 24, 72, and 144 h respectively; D, E, F – corresponding impedance spectra recorded at voltage of 0.5 V, amplitude 10 mV, wine red MEA C with Pt/C for comparison; bar graphs of resistances of MEAs obtained with EIS spectra fitting; ECSA (dash-dotted lines) and the respective remaining portions of ECSA relating to the first measurement (thinner, dashed lines) obtained using HUPD and CO stripping analyses. R_{Ω} is the ohmic resistance, $R_{CT,A}$ and $R_{CT,C}$ are the charge transfer resistances of the anode and cathode, respectively, R_{MT} is the mass transport resistance. In these graphs, KBb symbolises the MEA with PtCo/KB, rGOB stands for the MEA with PtCo/rGO and MEA C stands for Pt/C.

For both PtCo MEAs, the performance was rather poor, but the trends were different for each catalyst type. MEA KBb exhibited an underwhelming performance that was stable during the entire FC operation. MEA rGOB was overall slightly better (still worse than MEA C) with

gradual improvement during the operation. In terms of Tafel slopes, evaluated from *IR*-compensated dynamic load curves (see **Figure S5** and **Figure S6**) and listed in **Table S8**, significant changes are visible: $E_{\log j=0}$ of MEA rGOB grew significantly, which agrees with its activation during the experiment, while $E_{\log j=0}$ of MEA KBb remained nearly constant, as did its performance during operation (it is likely that cathode performance increase was compensated by the anode performance loss).

Table S8: $E_{\log j=0}$ (a) and slopes (b) evaluated from IR-compensated load curves of single cells with MEAs with novel catalysts on both electrodes. R^2 stands for the coefficient of determination of the linear fit.

MEA	$a_{24\text{ h}}$ V	$b_{24\text{ h}}$ V dec ⁻¹	R^2	$a_{72\text{ h}}$ V	$b_{72\text{ h}}$ V dec ⁻¹	R^2	$a_{144\text{ h}}$ V	$b_{144\text{ h}}$ V dec ⁻¹	R^2
MEA KBb	0.600	-0.120	0.98	0.614	-0.130	0.98	0.611	-0.127	0.98
MEA rGOB	0.514	-0.126	0.98	0.551	-0.137	0.98	0.585	-0.126	0.98
MEA C	0.582	-0.097	0.98	0.597	-0.088	0.98	0.591	-0.092	0.99

The EIS spectra in **Figure S19D**, **E** and **F** underline the mediocre performance of MEAs with PtCo catalysts on both electrodes. The R_{CT} values are fairly similar to those observed for the use of PtCo catalysts on the anodes. The R_{MT} observed for MEA KBb slightly increased (in the case of MEA rGOB, R_{MT} decreases) during operation, which could be a result of dealloying more pronounced than in MEA rGOB. It is not entirely clear why this R_{MT} for both the PtCo/KB and PtCo/rGO was lower when the catalyst was used on both electrodes in comparison with the use only on the anode.

Figure S19J, **K** and **L** then show *ECSA* on cathodes in the corresponding MEA experiments. The *ECSA* loss of MEA KBb resembles that of MEA C with its steeper fall between the first two measurements and subsequent slower rate of loss. The overall decrease of MEA KBb *ECSA* is also higher than in the case of MEA rGOB. Furthermore, the slight rise in the activity of PtCo/KB electrodes occurs between the first and second measurements (similarly to MEA KBc, see **Figures 1B**, **E** and **K**) which corresponds to the trends of *ECSA* loss due to the activation

of the electrode. The trend of ECSA loss in MEA rGO_b, determined by CO stripping and H_{UPD} analyses, is visibly similar to MEA rGO_c (see **Figure S19L and 1L**). It seems that the rate of ECSA loss is the same for PtCo/rGO regardless of the anode catalyst, i.e. $ECSA_{\text{HUPD}}$ is very stable, whereas $ECSA_{\text{CO}}$ gradually decreases. For both types of measurements, several phenomena, occurring during operation and discussed in more detail in the main text, play a role at the same time. As they have already been discussed, only a short summary is provided further in the text. H_3PO_4 gradually gets deeper in the catalyst layer and reaches more of the Pt surface, especially due to water formation in the cathode during cell operation. That way, the catalyst layer is being activated, although the phosphate anions adsorb on Pt. The catalyst nanoparticles also undergo degradation processes which counter the increasing active surface. As for the measurements, $ECSA_{\text{HUPD}}$ can be more stable than $ECSA_{\text{CO}}$ because of the easier access of protons to the active sites compared to CO. Possibly, the same phenomenon as in **Section 3.2** in the main text (the use of PtCo catalysts on the anode) could play a role – the presence of Co on the anode could affect the potential window from which the H_{UPD} charge is inferred, affecting the value of $ECSA_{\text{HUPD}}$.

The X-ray diffractograms in **Figure S20** document changes in MEAs after the operation with respect to the redistribution of Co. Trends are very similar for both PtCo catalysts. On the anode and anode side of the membrane, characteristic Pt reflections can be found at more positive angles, representing the presence of PtCo intermetallic nanoparticles. On the cathode and cathode side of the membrane, however, the reflections are shifted towards Pt, indicating the loss of Co, which is in line with results in previous sections. In this case, however, the presence of alloyed Co is still noticeable.

Figure S20: An excerpt of X-ray diffractograms of MEA KBb (A, B) and rGO (B, C) with experimental catalyst on both electrodes before (A, C) and after (B, D) the single cell experiments. The vertical lines show the positions of (111) and (100) reflections of pure Pt (black, full) and the PtCo alloys (red, dashed).

Based on the X-ray diffractograms, the size of crystallites (**Table S9**) was determined to be largely unchanged for both PtCo catalysts on the cathode, while on the anode, the sizes seem to have decreased. The reason for this phenomenon remains unclear.

Table S9: Dimensions of Pt NPs in the direction perpendicular to the Pt(111) facet of pristine GDEs and parts of MEAs used in the experiments with PtCo catalysts on both electrodes (MEA KBb and rGO), Pt/C for comparison.

Catalyst in MEA	Pristine GDE	Anode	Membrane anode	Cathode	Membrane cathode
PtCo/KB; sizes/nm	4.5	-	3.3	5.9	4.5
PtCo/rGO; sizes/nm	5.4	-	3.9	5.4	4.6
Pt/C; sizes/nm	5.3	9.7	5.6	5.3	8.4

Table S10 shows the Pt:Co mass ratios in the same manner as in previous chapters. For MEA KBb, it seems that considerable Co dissolution occurs on the cathode, which then results in its transport towards the anode and subsequent lower Pt:Co ratios there. As for MEA rGO_b, it is harder to draw conclusions, since during the delamination of the electrodes, most of the anode CL stayed on the membrane, whereas the cathode delaminated from the membrane almost intact. Thus, the precision of XRF results is, in this case, lower and it is harder to compare the two sides. Regarding the CL that stayed on the electrodes of MEA rGO_b, the Pt:Co ratio is lower than the original value in both the cathode and anode; however, for the cathode, the ratio is surprisingly low and suggests a considerable loss of Pt. Turning the attention to the respective sides of the membrane, the trend is different, and both sides show a higher Pt:Co ratio, as if most of Pt from the electrodes stayed in the part of the CLs closer to the membrane.

Table S10: Mass ratios of Pt to Co on electrodes and the respective sides of the membranes from MEAs used in experiments with novel catalysts on both electrodes (MEA KBb and rGO_b).

Sample	PtCo/KB			PtCo/rGO		
	Pristine GDE	Cathode	Anode	Pristine GDE	Cathode	Anode
Electrodes	13.1	11.9	6.4	7.9	4.4	6.0
Membranes		16.1	14.5		13.3	11.2

The white line intensity plots in **Figure S21** show, similarly to the previous cases, lower oxidation of Pt atoms on the cathode after operation (**Figure S21A**), although for MEA rGO_b the difference is not that stark. In **Figure S21B** more Co in a higher oxidation state is observed for PtCo/rGO at the cathode, while at the anode and membrane, a lower difference is visible, as there is significantly more of the alloyed Co. Interestingly, Co seems to be more oxidised on the anode in MEA KBb, possibly suggesting harder transport of Co phosphates from nanoparticles than in rGO.

Figure S21: White line intensities for MEAs C, KBb and rGOB at the Pt L₃-edge (A) and at the Co K-edge (B). The MEAs themselves are bordered by a rectangle, next to which bars of pristine materials are shown. A, M, and C represent anode, membrane, and cathode, respectively.

As for the EXAFS results, MEAs rGOB and KBb behave very similarly to MEAs rGOa and KBa in the Pt L₃-edge (**Figure S11**). In the Co K-edge, the results suggest that there is alloyed Co present in the cathodes, but they also show high degree of Co phosphate presence (**Figure S12**).